

DESCRIPTION OF THE PROBLEMS OF TRANSLATING PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN LITERARY WORKS

Shirin Alisherovna Khamrabaeva

Lecturer, Tashkent state university of Oriental studies

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Abstract

This article analyzes the problems that arise in the process of translating phraseological units found in works of art into another language. The author substantiates the close connection of phraseologisms with national culture and mentality, and the possibility of distortion of meaning as a result of their literal translation. The article highlights various translation methods of phraseological units, in particular, equivalent, analog and descriptive translation methods, based on examples. It is also emphasized that the translator's linguoculturological knowledge and creative approach play a great role in this process.

Keywords: phraseologism, translation problem, work of art, equivalent translation, linguoculturology, national color, mentality, contextual compatibility

Introduction: In modern translation studies, the process of translating works of art is interpreted not only as a language, but also as a process of intercultural communication and understanding. In particular, the translation of phraseological units used in a literary text is one of the most complex and delicate aspects of this process. Phraseologisms are stable expressions in a language that are directly related to the historical memory, worldview and culture of each people. They serve as a means of figurativeness, expressiveness, national color and emotional expression in the language. Therefore, their correct and concise translation into another language poses many linguistic and cultural issues for the translator.

Problems that arise when translating phraseological units are often associated with the fact that their direct equivalent does not exist in another language, they acquire a different meaning in the context, or they express a content inherent in national traditions and customs. In such cases, the translator is forced to abandon the literal translation method and resort to methods such as phraseological equivalent, functional analogue or descriptive translation. This relies not only on the translator's knowledge of the language, but also on his deep understanding of the source and target language culture, artistic thinking and creative approach.

This article focuses on this issue and objectively analyzes the ways of correctly understanding and adequately translating phraseologisms in the

translation of literary works, existing methods, their effectiveness, and emerging problems. During the analysis, reasoning is based on practical materials on the example of literary texts in English, Russian, and Uzbek. The purpose of the article is to identify current problems in the translation of phraseologisms, to provide suggestions for their solution, and to highlight the theoretical and practical significance of the study of phraseological units in translation studies.

Main part: Phraseological units are semantically coherent, but grammatically and lexically complex expressions. They often express not a direct lexical meaning, but a portable, connotative meaning. Each people, during its historical development, socio-cultural life, forms phraseological expressions that express various states, feelings and relationships through unique images and symbols. Therefore, phraseological units are inextricably linked with the mentality, thinking, and values of the people, and it is important to take into account the cultural context when translating them.

The translation of phraseological units in literary translation poses the following main problems: Many phraseological units do not have a direct equivalent in another language. For example, the Uzbek expression "to put sand in one's ear" cannot be translated exactly into English or Russian. Since phraseologisms are based on elements specific to national culture, they may not be understood by a foreign language user. When some phraseologisms are taken out of context or misinterpreted, the original meaning is distorted. The correct translation of phraseologisms depends not only on the translator's knowledge of the language, but also on his intercultural communicative potential and creative approach.

The following methods are used when translating phraseological units:

Translation by full equivalent In this method, if there is an alternative to the source language phraseologism that is compatible in meaning and form, it is translated directly.

For example: "To flirt with someone" - to meet someone's gaze

Functional analogue (synonymous expression) It is translated through a phraseological combination that is similar in meaning, although it differs in form.

For example: "Don't rack your brain" - Don't rack your brain

Descriptive translation The meaning of a phraseological unit is explained using simple words.

For example: "Snow fell on his face" - He felt deeply ashamed

Literal translation Sometimes a phraseological unit retains its meaning even if translated literally, but this method should be used very carefully.

For example: "It turned a blind eye" - if this English expression is translated literally into Uzbek as "blind", the meaning will be distorted.

The translation of phraseological units is one of the most complex, responsible and delicate aspects of literary translation. They increase the level of figurativeness of the language, reveal the specific features of national culture and give stylistic richness to the literary text. Therefore, the correct, natural and contextual translation of phraseological units into another language poses not only linguistic, but also cultural, psychological and creative problems for the translator.

The research conducted in the article has shown that there is no single approach to the translation of phraseological units. Each phraseological unit requires an individual approach, taking into account the specific context, the general spirit of the work, the author's style and the cultural characteristics of the target language. The methods used in translation - direct equivalent, functional analogue, descriptive translation or word-for-word approach - are selected depending on the situation. In particular, functional and descriptive translations serve as an important tool for conveying phraseological units in an understandable way to the reader while preserving their meaning.

To successfully translate phraseological units, a translator must have the following abilities:

deep knowledge of the phraseological reserve of the source and target languages;

understanding of intercultural thinking and differences;

in-depth analysis of the general context of a work of art;

ability to apply a creative and stylistic approach.

It is also necessary to study in-depth the theoretical foundations of the translation of phraseological units and improve translation skills through practical exercises. In the future, further expansion of research in this area, enrichment of the base of phraseological dictionaries, and integration of computer linguistics tools into the process of phraseological translation remain urgent tasks.

In conclusion, translating phraseological units is not a simple language exchange, but rather building a bridge of cultural and spiritual thinking. This makes the translator an active participant in intercultural communication rather than a language intermediary.

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